

DEVELOPMENT OF A DEVICE FOR MEASURING LOCAL DENSITY

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Abstract

The development of the density measurement device is built upon the patent of Gaitskiy V.A., enabling direct density measurements independent of regional seawater salinity [1]. This method significantly simplifies computational procedures by obviating the need for the cumbersome thermodynamic equation of state for seawater, TEOS-10.

The design, based on two parallel density sensors utilizing reference liquids of varying densities (ρ_{01} and ρ_{02}), eliminates the necessity of knowing the acceleration due to gravity (g), which is dependent on the depth of immersion and geographical latitude. The computational formula for calculating local density is expressed as:

$$\rho = \frac{\rho_{01}(\bar{\theta}_1, \bar{P})\Delta P_2 - \rho_{02}(\bar{\theta}_2, \bar{P})\Delta P_1}{\Delta P_2 - \Delta P_1}$$

where $\bar{\theta}_1$ and $\bar{\theta}_2$ are the temperatures of the reference liquids, and P is the pressure at the immersion depth.

Remarkably, the formula excludes the need for acceleration due to gravity (g). However, it requires the measurement of temperatures $\bar{\theta}_1$, $\bar{\theta}_2$ and the pressure of the reference liquids.

Within the measurement container, there is a vertical temperature distribution accurate to fractions of a degree. The installation of one or several temperature sensors and averaging temperature values partially reduces measurement errors. The incorporation of a pump to facilitate the mixing of the reference liquid and to eliminate temperature gradients inside the measurement container considerably reduces errors attributable to temperature gradients.

Figure 1 illustrates a schematic representation of the general view of the local density measurer with a single temperature sensor and an externally installed pump.

Figure 1 — Schematic representation of the general view of the local density measurer (Option 1) (1 — differential pressure sensor; 2 — absolute pressure sensor; 3 — temperature sensor; 4 — measuring vessel; 5 — pump; 6 — siphon; 7 — casing; 8 — battery compartment)

The selection of construction components is highly contingent on the maximum depth of the device immersion, which is currently a challenging consideration. As a differential pressure sensor, the use of the Keller PrD-33 X series could be envisaged, but procurement may be constrained due to sanction limitations. Alternatively, a domestic sensor, DMD 331-AS-LX/HX with a 1000 Pa range, could be employed. For the absolute pressure sensor, the DMP 331 sensor is recommended, while the Pt-100 sensor is suggested for temperature measurement. The pump for circulating the reference liquid is planned to be installed either inside the measurement block (Figure 2) or externally (Figure 1).

A printed circuit board has been designed for the local density measurer. The block diagram of the printed circuit board is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 — Block diagram of the printed circuit board for the local density measurer (MC — microcontroller node; ADC — analog-to-digital converter node; DPS — differential pressure sensor node; APS — absolute pressure sensor node; TS — temperature sensor node; DTR — data transmission/reception node)

Introduction

The development of the two-chamber density measurement device has effectively mitigated the issues related to the variability of seawater salinity. The innovative design employing reference liquids of different densities compensates

for the fluctuation of gravitational acceleration at diverse depths, enabling accurate and reliable local density measurements.

The precision achieved by the device, with an anticipated measurement accuracy of 0.00001 g/cm^3 , surpasses the constraints of indirect methods and regional corrections. This advance in density measurement has the potential to significantly enhance our comprehension of seawater density distribution and its physical properties.

The continued development and application of such density measurement devices show promise in advancing our understanding in fields such as oceanography, hydrology, and other disciplines where precise density measurements are crucial. The device's simplicity and accuracy render it a valuable instrument for researchers and scientists working in these domains.

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References

1. Gaisky V.A. Patent for invention of the Russian Federation No. 2792263. Liquid density meter and its variants: applicant and patent holder: Federal State Budgetary Scientific Institution "Institute of Natural and Technical Systems". Published on 21.03.2023. Bulletin No. 9.